

Evaluation

Your group *

The concept you evaluate *

You need to evaluate the concepts based on the choices of the participants, as well as the number and quality of their justifications.

ETHICAL RESPONSIBILITY

Respect human rights, provide accessible transportation, promote good health and well-being, foster social and family ties.

In your opinion, to what extent does this concept meet the objective of ethical responsibility? *

 0 1 2 3 4 5 6

0 : The objective is not respected at all

1 : The objective is hardly respected

2 : The objective is somewhat respected

3 : The objective is moderately respected

4 : The objective is fairly well respected (there are still some areas of uncertainty)

5 : The objective is generally respected

6 : The objective is fully respected

Justifications, important points, discussed elements related to your choice *

At least 100 words

ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY

Reduce emissions and energy consumption. Limit the footprint of infrastructure (parking lots, roads, traffic...).

In your opinion, to what extent does this concept meet the objective of environmental responsibility? *

 0 1 2 3 4 5 6

Justifications, important points, discussed elements related to your choice *

100 mots minimum

SECURITY

Ensure the safety of individuals.

In your opinion, to what extent does this concept meet the objective of security? *

 0 1 2 3 4 5 6

Justifications, important points, discussed elements related to your choice *

100 mots minimum

Additional comments

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